

2-Aminothiazole Derivatives. Part I

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A series of 2-amino-4-benzyl- and 4-benzoyl-thiazoles along with their 2-acetamido-5-chloromercuri and 2-acetamido-5-bromo derivatives have been prepared with a view to studying their chemotherapeutic properties. 2-Amino-4-benzoyl- and 4-benzylthiazoles have been obtained by condensing 1-phenyl-3-bromo-1,2-propanediones and 1-chloro-3-phenylacetones respectively with thiourea. The acetamido derivatives of these thiazole bases, when treated with HgCl_2 solution, give corresponding 5-chloromercuri derivatives which, have further been converted to 5-bromo derivatives by the action of bromine. Some of the compounds are found to be bacteriostatic *in vitro* tests against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*.

In view of the good response shown by 2-amino-4-arylthiazoles and their derivatives as antibacterials¹ and as fungicides², it was considered of interest to synthesise 2-aminothiazole derivatives having various substituents at 4-position. Rout and Mahapatra³ showed that introduction of halogen, particularly bromine, into thiazole nucleus definitely enhanced bactericidal and fungicidal activity, but Paik⁴ found 2-amino-5-bromothiazole to be very active amongst the compounds tested for tuberculostatic activity. It was therefore decided to synthesise 2-amino-4-aryl-5-bromothiazole derivatives. The encouraging results obtained by Mahapatra⁵ and Das *et al.*⁶ regarding pronounced fungicidal as well as bactericidal properties of mercurated 2-anilino-4-arylthiazoles also indicated a further investigation of mercurated 2-aminothiazole derivatives. In view of the above considerations the following types of compounds have been prepared in the present work with the hope of discovering suitable antibacterial or antifungal agents.

2-Amino-4-benzoyl or benzylthiazoles and their 2-acetamido-5-chloromercuri or 5-bromo derivatives.

[X=CO or CH₂ and Y=HgCl or Br; R=R₁=H, Cl, or OMe and R₂=H, Cl, Me, OMe or NO₂]

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1. Yoshio *et al.*, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1951, 71, 709.
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3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2427.
4. Ann. Rept. Research Inst. Tuberc., Kanazawa Univ., 1953, 11, No. 2, 30.
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1-Phenyl-1,2-propan-diones, obtained from propiophenones on oximation and subsequent hydrolysis of the α -isonitrosopropiophenones, were brominated in sunlight to the corresponding 1-phenyl-3-bromo-1,2-propan-diones. These bromoketones were condensed with equimolecular quantity of thiourea to afford 2-amino-4-benzoylthiazole hydrobromides which on basification gave respective thiazole bases. Since preparation of 2-amino-4-benzylthiazoles from 2-amino-4-benzoylthiazoles by Clemmensen's reduction resulted in very poor yields, these were synthesised independently by condensing 1-chloro-3-phenylacetones with equimolecular quantity of thiourea in ethanol. These acetones were obtained from various phenylacetic acids by the action of diazomethane on their acid chlorides and subsequent decomposition of the diazoketones by HCl.

2-Acetamido-4-benzoyl-and-benzylthiazoles were chloromercurated according to the procedure of Hurd and Wehrmeister⁷ to the corresponding 5-chloromercuri compounds by adding HgCl₂ solution to a hot ethanolic solution of the compounds. These chloromercuri derivatives were further converted to respective 5-bromo derivatives by the action of bromine. That chloromercuration, and hence replacement of chloromercuri group by bromine, takes place only at 5-position and never in the phenyl ring of 2-acetamido-4-benzoyl- and -benzylthiazoles has been proved by oxidising individually 2-acetamido-4-benzoyl-5-bromothiazole and 2-acetamido-4-benzyl-5-bromothiazole to benzoic acid only.

Some of the 2-amino-4-benzoyl- and -benzylthiazoles, their hydrochlorides and their 2-acetamido-5-bromo derivatives were found to be bacteriostatic *in vitro* when tested against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. The detailed results of the testing will be published elsewhere.

EXPERIMENTAL

Various propiophenones and acetophenones were prepared by the Friedel-Crafts reaction on substituted benzenes. α -Isonitrosopropiophenones were prepared according to Blatt.⁸ α -Isonitroso-2',4'-dichloropropiophenone and its 3',4'-dichloro and 2',5'-dichloro isomers melting at 115-6°, 158-69° and 147-48° respectively, are new compounds. They gave analyses correctly for their N and Cl contents. Various phenylacetic acids were prepared from the acetophenones through Kindler's modification of Willgerodt reaction using morpholine and sulphur.

1-Phenyl-1,2-propan-diones.—In a litre r.b. flask arranged for steam distillation, a mixture of α -isonitrosopropiophenone and 10-15% H₂SO₄ in proportion of 1:10 (by weight) was steam distilled until last portion of the distillate did not contain any oily droplets. The heavy oil or solid from the distillate was separated; aqueous portion was extracted with ether after saturating with common salt and the combined ether extract was washed with 2% sodium bicarbonate solution and dried (Na₂SO₄). Solvent was removed and the residue purified either by distillation under reduced pressure or by crystallisation from a suitable solvent. These are described in Table I.

7. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 4007.

8. "Organic Syntheses, Collective Volume II", 1950, p. 363.

TABLE I

1-Phenyl-1,2-propan-diones.

S.No.	Substituents in phenyl ring.	Yield.	M.P.	B.P.	Found.	Ref.:
1	4'-Methyl	60%	..	117-20°/5	C : 74.23% H : 6.20	74.08% 6.17
2	4'-Methoxy*	60	46-47°	..	C : 67.31 H : 5.79	67.42 5.62
3	4'-Chloro	50	..	140-44°/20	Cl : 19.52	19.45
4	4'-Nitro*	59	91-92°	..	N : 7.35	7.25
5	2',4'-Dichloro	40	..	142-47°/10	Cl : 32.88	32.72
6	3',4'-Dichloro	40	47-48°	..	Cl : 32.61	32.72
7	2',5'-Dichloro	38	..	154-57°/12	Cl : 32.68	32.72

*Described in literature by different methods.

2-Amino-4-benzoylthiazoles

General Method.—1-Phenyl-1,2-propan-dione (0.02M) was brominated in sunlight by adding dropwise, the required quantity of bromine in CS₂ to the boiling solution of the compound in CS₂ (50 ml). After refluxing for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, the solvent was removed, residue taken in ether, ether solution washed with 2% sodium thiosulphate solution, and dried (Na₂SO₄). Powdered thiourea (0.02 M) was added to the dry ethereal solution; soon an exothermic reaction started and the reaction mixture was then gently refluxed for 30 minutes. The crude product was filtered, washed with ether, residue suspended in water, and basified with dilute ammonia to give free base. These aminoketones were characterised by preparing acetyl, hydrochloride and semicarbazone derivatives. Various ketones along with their derivatives are described in Table II.

2-Acetamido-4-benzoyl-5-bromothiazoles.—To a hot ethanolic solution of 2-acetamido-4-benzoylthiazole (0.5 g.) was added, with shaking, an aqueous solution containing HgCl₂ (0.7 g.) and sodium acetate (1.2 g.). White precipitate of 5-chloromercuri derivative soon separated and the mixture was refluxed for an hour. It was cooled, filtered, residue washed successively with hot water, ethanol and ether, and then dried in the air. The chloromercuri compound was purified by dissolving it in glacial acetic acid and regenerating on dilution. To a saturated solution of sodium bromide in methanol (15 ml) was added a chloromercuri compound (0.5 g.) followed by further addition of a few drops of bromine till red colour persisted. The mixture was well shaken to form a clear solution, some sodium sulphite added to remove excess of bromine, and heated under reflux for 30 minutes. The hot reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate concentrated and diluted with a minimum quantity of water. The solid separating was filtered and crystallised from a suitable solvent. Various 2-acetamido-4-benzoyl-5-chloro and -5-bromo-mercurithiazoles are described in Table II,

TABLE II

2-Amino-4-benzoylthiazoles and their derivatives.

S.No.	Name.	Yield.	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
1	2-Amino-4-benzoylthiazole	66%	160-61°	N : 13.59%	13.73%
	2-Acetamido deriv.	..	195-96°	S : 15.82	15.69
	Hydrochloride	..	98-99°	N : 11.21	11.39
	Semicarbazone	..	220-21°(d)	S : 13.23	13.01
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri	..	273-74°	N : 11.88	11.64
	2-Acetamido-5-bromo- ,,	..	190-200°	N : 27.00	26.62
				N : 5.70	5.83
2	2-Amino-4-(4'-methyl-benzoyl) thiazole	70	153-54°	N : 8.50	8.62
	2-Acetamido deriv.	..	200-201°	S : 9.66	9.84
	Hydrochloride	..	215-16°	N : 12.76	12.84
	Semicarbazone	..	208° (decomp.)	S : 14.79	14.68
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri	..	285-86°	N : 11.02	10.76
	2-Acetamido-5-bromo- ,,	..	168-69°	S : 12.17	12.30
				N : 10.89	11.00
3	2-Amino-4-(4'-methoxy-benzoyl) thiazole	67	155-56°	N : 24.98	25.46
	2-Acetamido deriv.	..	197-98°	N : 5.72	5.66
	Hydrochloride	..	222° (decomp.)	N : 8.10	8.26
	Semicarbazone	..	231° (decomp.)	S : 9.25	9.44
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri	..	284° (blackens)	N : 12.03	11.97
	2-Acetamido-5-bromo- ,,	..	177-78°	S : 13.68	13.68
				N : 10.05	10.15
4	2-Amino-4-(4'-chloro-benzoyl) thiazole	67	157-58°	S : 11.44	11.60
	2-Acetamido deriv.	..	217-18°	N, 10.44	10.35
	Hydrochloride	..	234-35°	N : 23.95	24.05
	Semicarbazone	..	207° (decomp.)	N : 5.40	5.48
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri	..	288-89°	N : 8.00	7.99
	2-Acetamido-5-bromo- ,,	..	177-78°	S : 9.20	9.01
				N : 11.81	11.74
5	2-Amino-4-(2', 4'-dichloro-benzoyl) thiazole	47	203-204°	S : 13.28	13.42
	2-Acetamido deriv.	..	179-80°	N : 9.83	9.98
	Hydrochloride	..	209-10°	S : 11.57	11.40
	Semicarbazone	..	198° (decomp)	N : 10.32	10.18
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri	..	255° (blackens)	N : 23.89	23.69
	2-Acetamido-5-bromo- ,,	..	206-207°	N : 5.34	5.44
				N : 7.59	7.79
			S : 9.11	8.90	
			N : 10.38	10.26	
			S : 11.53	11.71	
			N : 8.80	8.89	
			S : 9.69	10.16	
			N : 8.95	9.04	
			N : 20.78	21.22	
			N : 4.98	5.09	
			N : 7.21	7.10	
			S : 7.97	8.12	

TABLE II (contd.)

S.No.	Name	Yield	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
6	2-Amino-4-(3',4'-dichloro-benzoyl) thiazole	50	198-99°	N : 10.18%	10.28%
	2-Acetamido deriv.	..	217-18°	S : 11.96	11.71
				N : 9.06	8.89
				S : 10.38	10.16
	Hydrochloride	..	215-16°	N : 9.10	9.04
	Semicarbazone	..	174-75°	N : 21.45	21.22
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri	..	282-83°	N : 5.21	5.09
7	2-Amino-4-(2',5'-dichloro-benzoyl) thiazole	47	168-60°	N : 7.24	7.10
	2-Acetamido deriv.	..	190-01°	S : 8.07	8.12
				N : 10.35	10.26
				S : 11.55	11.71
	Hydrochloride	..	202-203°	N : 8.59	8.89
	Semicarbazone	..	204° (decomp.)	S : 10.30	10.16
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri	..	255° (decomp.)	N : 8.00	9.04
	2-Acetamido-5-bromo- ..	..	200-201°	N : 21.06	21.22
				N : 5.26	5.09
				N : 6.91	7.10
			S : 8.23	8.12	

1.-Chloro-3-phenylacetones.—To an ice-cold solution of diazomethane in ether (obtained from 25 g. of nitrosomonoc methylurea and 75ml of 50% KOH) was added with stirring an ice-cold solution of phenylacetyl chloride (0.05M.) in ether below 5° and stirring continued for about 5 hours. Dry HCl was then passed till evolution of nitrogen gas had ceased and the mixture was left for 2 hours. It was poured over crushed ice, ether layer separated, washed with water and 5% sodium carbonate solution, and dried (Na₂SO₄). Solvent was removed and the residue purified by either distillation under reduced pressure or by crystallisation from a suitable solvent. These are described in Table III.

TABLE III

1-Chloro-3-phenylacetones.

S.No.	Substituents in phenyl ring.	Yield.	M.P.	B.P.	%Chlorine	
					Found.	Reqd.
1.	4'-Methyl	80%	..	135-40°/7 mm	19.54	19.45
2.	4'-Methoxy	78	..	161-63°/15	18.01	17.89
3.	4'-Chloro	75	..	155-60°/6	35.18	34.98
4.	2',4'-Dichloro	80	72-73°	..	44.98	44.85
5.	2',5'-Dichloro	78	73-74°	..	44.59	44.85
6.	3',4'-Dichloro	75	..	170-76°/10	44.61	44.85
7.	2'-Chloro-4'-methoxy	75	..	172-76°/8	30.88	30.47

2-Amino-4-benzylthiazoles.—A mixture of 1-chloro-3-phenylacetone (0.02 *M*), powdered thiourea (0.02 *M*), and ethanol (20-25ml) was heated under reflux for about 4 hours. The solvent was removed under diminished pressure and the residue was basified with dilute ammonia to liberate the free base. These thiazole bases were characterised by preparing acetyl derivatives (Table IV).

TABLE IV

2-Amino-4-benzylthiazoles and their derivatives.

S.No.	Name.	Yield.	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	2-Amino-4-benzylthiazole*	70%	92-93°	N : 14.91%	14.73%
	2-Acetamido deriv.	..	190-91°	N : 12.14	12.07
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri	..	201° (decomp.)	N : 6.22	6.00
	2-Acetamido-5-bromo- ..	..	164-65°	N : 9.14	9.00
2.	2-Amino-4-(4'-methylbenzyl)-thiazole	73	109-10°	S : 10.47	10.29
	2-Acetamido deriv.	..	147-48°	N : 13.59	13.73
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri	..	264-65°	S : 15.76	15.69
	2-Acetamido-5-bromo- ..	..	177-78°	N : 11.51	11.39
				S : 12.82	13.01
				N : 5.91	5.83
3.	2-Amino-4-(4'-methoxybenzyl) thiazole	75	186-87°	N : 8.48	8.61
	2-Acetamido deriv.	..	190-91°	S : 0.93	0.84
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri	..	258-59°	N : 12.55	12.73
	2-Acetamido-5-bromo- ..	..	163-64°	S : 14.71	14.54
4.	2-Amino-4-(4'-chlorobenzyl) thiazole	68	141-42°	N : 10.75	10.69
	2-Acetamido deriv.	..	166-67°	S : 12.08	12.21
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri	..	271-72°	N : 5.55	5.64
	2-Acetamido-5-bromo- ..	..	182-83°	N : 8.40	8.21
				S : 9.19	9.38
				N : 12.29	12.47
5.	2-Amino-4-(2',4'-dichlorobenzyl) thiazole	70	97-98°	Cl : 16.05	15.81
	2-Acetamido deriv.	70	184-85°	N : 10.63	10.51
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri	..	271-72°	Cl : 13.51	13.32
	2-Acetamido-5-bromo- ..	..	182-83°	N : 5.45	5.59
				N : 8.25	8.10
				S : 8.24	8.06
	2-Amino-4-(2',4'-dichlorobenzyl) thiazole	70	97-98°	N : 10.50	10.81
	2-Acetamido deriv.	70	184-85°	Cl : 27.55	27.41
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri	..	286-87°	N : 9.50	9.30
	2-Acetamido-5-bromo- ..	..	200-201°	Cl : 23.60	23.59
			N : 5.50	5.23	
			N : 7.21	7.37	
			S : 8.60	8.42	

TABLE IV (contd.)

S.No.	Name.	Yield.	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
6.	2-Amino-4-(2',5'-dichloro-benzyl) thiazole 2-Acetamido deriv.	67 ..	104-105° 180-90°	N : 10.80%	10.81%
				Cl : 27.36	27.41
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri 2-Acetamido-5-bromo- "		285-86° 181-82°	N : 9.25	9.30
				Cl : 23.39	23.56
				N : 5.14	5.23
				N : 7.21	7.37
7.	2-Amino-4-(3',4'-dichloro-benzyl) thiazole 2-Acetamido deriv.	72 ..	110-20° 155-56°	S : 8.24	8.42
				N : 10.75	10.81
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri 2-Acetamido-5-bromo- "		280-81° 235-36°	Cl : 27.56	27.41
				N : 9.11	9.30
				Cl : 23.71	23.59
				N : 5.34	5.23
8.	2-Amino-4-(2'-chloro-4'-methoxybenzyl) thiazole 2-Acetamido deriv.	70 ..	140-41° 160-70°	N : 7.40	7.37
				S : 8.27	8.42
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri 2-Acetamido-5-bromo- "		280-90° 189-90°	N : 11.21	11.00
				Cl : 13.88	13.95
				N : 9.51	9.44
				Cl : 12.15	11.98
9.	2-Amino-4-(4'-nitrobenzyl)-thiazole* 2-Acetamido deriv.	65 ..	172-73° 198-80°	N : 5.38	5.27
				N : 7.40	7.46
	2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri 2-Acetamido-5-bromo- "		269-70° 185-86°	S : 9.71	8.52
				N : 17.95	17.66
				N : 15.30	15.16
				S : 11.38	11.55
2-Acetamido-5-chloromercuri 2-Acetamido-5-bromo- "		269-70° 185-86°	N : 8.37	8.21	
			N : 12.01	11.80	
				S : 9.18	8.99

*Kenji Kaji *et al.*, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1955, 75, 438.

2-Acetamido-4-benzyl-5-bromothiazoles were prepared according to the procedure adopted for 2-acetamido-4-benzoyl-5-bromothiazoles. Various 5-chloromercuri and 5-bromo derivatives are described in Table IV.

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